

Influence of Moisture on the Electrical Conductance of Lead Nitrate Crystals

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The influence of moisture on the electrical conductance of lead nitrate has been investigated. It has been observed that the conductance increases with the relative humidity of the environment. A mechanism involving adsorption, absorption, diffusion and ionization has been suggested to explain the effect.

SEVERAL studies have been made by various workers on the ionic conductivity of inorganic crystals particularly the alkali metal halides and it has been accepted generally that the conductance of crystals is ordinarily due to the motion of free positive ion vacancies having an apparent negative charge¹. The positive ion vacancies are considerably mobile and the conductance of the crystal can be considered as a direct measure of the number of positive ion vacancies.

It has also been observed that the conductance of potassium bromide and potassium iodide increases in the presence of bromine and iodine vapours respectively². The fact that water can penetrate rock salt has been confirmed by infrared absorption spectrum³. A number of workers have observed slow sorption processes for the following systems⁴: sulphur dioxide in sodium chloride, hydrogen chloride in potassium chloride, and ammonia in sodium chloride.

During the course of some of the investigations on the electrical conductance of lead nitrate crystals in this laboratory it has been observed that traces of moisture produce appreciable effect on the conductance of the system. It was, therefore, of interest to investigate in detail the influence of moisture on the electrical conductance of lead nitrate crystals and the present study was undertaken.

Experimental

Analytical reagent grade (E. Merck) lead nitrate was used for the investigations. Crystals of lead nitrate in the form of tablets (diameter, 6 mm; length 5-7 mm) prepared under a pressure of 20 tons per square inch with an Amsler machine (Alfred J. Amsler & Co., Switzerland) and a steel die were used for conductance measurements. The samples were held under pressure by two loaded springs between brass discs covered with platinum foil which served as electrodes. The surfaces in contact

with the electrodes were painted with Conductive Silver Composition 4817 (E.I. du Pont de Nemours & Co., U.S.A.) for better electrical contact. A microammeter (Model No. 350, Taylor Electrical Instruments Ltd., Slough, Bucks., England) was used to measure the conductance of the samples. Ohm's law was obeyed and no polarization effects were observed.

To study the influence of moisture on the electrical conductance of lead nitrate, the conductance was measured by keeping the samples in various humidity-controlled atmospheres for periods up to 24 hr, by which time a state of equilibrium was attained. The constant humidity-controlled environments were obtained by taking mixtures of sulphuric acid and water in the proportions⁵ (in terms of density) given below:

Density of sulphuric acid-water mixture	Relative humidity, per cent.
1.1	93.9
1.15	88.8
1.2	80.5
1.25	70.4
1.3	58.3

The samples for conductance measurements were placed over these mixtures in desiccators.

To start with, the conductance of the tablet after desiccating it over phosphorus pentoxide in a desiccator for 48 hr. was measured. The sample was then transferred and kept over the sulphuric acid-water mixture taken in a desiccator, the connecting wires were taken out through the hole in the wall of the desiccator, the hole being sealed air tight with sealing wax. The conductance of the sample was then measured. The tablet was allowed to remain in the constant relative humidity atmosphere in the desiccator and its conductance was measured at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 15, 20 and 24 hr. It was then desiccated thoroughly over phosphorus

pentoxide and then used for conductance measurements in another humidity-controlled atmosphere as before. A constant potential of 12 volts, d.c., was applied for the measurements.

Results

Data on the influence of moisture on the electrical conductance of lead nitrate are presented graphically in Fig. 1. For a given relative humidity

Fig. 1. Variation of conductance with time.

- RH 70.4
- △ RH 80.5
- RH 85.0
- RH 88.0
- ▽ RH 93.9

there is a rapid rise in the electrical conductance in the beginning, up to 10 hr., and then slows down monotonically. For example, at a relative humidity of 85.0 per cent. the current at 0 hr. is 0.05 microampere and 5.2 after 5 hr., 5.95 after 10 hr. whereafter it becomes steady over a period of 24 hr. It is of interest to note that the rate of increase is greater at higher relative humidities of the environment.

Discussions

The current-time relationships represented in Fig. 1 are similar to those obtained by Mc Bain⁶ for the adsorption of iodine by carbon where the rate of adsorption is very high at first but drops off fairly steeply after the first few minutes. It is evident from these plots that the rate of increase is very high at first, up to 10 hr., and then almost a constant for a period of 24 hr. The similarity of these plots with those of Mc Bain⁶ suggests that the mechanism involved in both the cases is similar. Saturation curves similar to that obtained here have been obtained by Tryhorn and Wyatt⁷ for the adsorption of vapours of pure liquids, viz. CH_3OH , CS_2 , $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$, H_2O , $\text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$ and $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$, on coconut charcoal.

Bangham and Burt⁸ have observed that the time relationship of adsorption of gases by solids obey the simple law

$$S^m = kt \quad \dots (1)$$

where S is the amount of adsorption up to the time t after admission of gas and m is a constant which may have a value as high as 12 depending on various factors. Herbert⁴, and Bangham and Burt⁸ have also observed similar relationship to hold good for adsorption of SO_2 and NH_3 respectively.

Fig. 2. Variation of $\log c$ with $\log t$.

- RH 70.4
- △ RH 80.5
- RH 85.0
- ▽ RH 88.6

In Fig. 2 are plotted logarithm of the equilibrium current against logarithm of time of exposure of the sample to moisture up to 10 hr. during which period a steady state of equilibrium has been established as indicated by the plots in Fig. 1. The linear plots in Fig. 2 show that an equation of the type

$$c^m = kt \quad \dots (2)$$

where c is the equilibrium current, holds good. Therefore it is possible that the process involved is one of adsorption. The plots in Fig. 2 are parallel with $m=0.44$ in agreement with the above equation and the classical Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

Davis⁹ has shown that adsorption is invariably followed by absorption. The water vapours that are adsorbed by the crystals are therefore absorbed and pass into the interior of the crystals. Studies on the conductance of potassium bromide and potassium iodide in the presence of bromine and iodine vapours respectively have revealed that the conductance of these substances increased in the presence of these vapours². The solute, here the vapour, is most likely dispersed along the crystal defects and glide planes in the crystal. The mere introduction of a foreign molecule into a perfect lattice would distort the lattice locally and create a defect¹⁰. It has also been proved that water can penetrate rock salt⁴. It is likely, therefore, that the water vapours taken up by adsorption accompanied by absorption enter into the crystal lattice and create

defects in the lattice. The water molecules which penetrate into the lattice weaken the binding forces due to its fairly large magnitude of the dielectric constant ; as a result the electrons inside the lattice become more mobile. These mobile electrons pass much easily to the conduction level and the conductivity of the crystal increases.

It is evident from Fig. 1 that the conductance increases with increase of the relative humidity. It has been shown by Warburg¹¹ that an application of an electromotive force can bring about diffusion in an ionic crystal. The increased adsorption of moisture at higher relative humidities is thus facilitated by the applied potential through increased diffusion and hence results in an increase of current.

Thus it is possible that an adsorption mechanism is operative and the water molecules which enter the crystals alter the mobility of the electrons and bring them to the conduction level. The water molecules also increase the ionization resulting in an increase in the conductance of the crystal. As the atmosphere surrounding the crystals becomes richer in water vapour, the amount of water vapour absorbed increases and hence there will be a rapid change in the conductance at higher relative humidities.

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